

Effects of field application of nutrients on grain yield of iron-tolerant CK4 and susceptible Bouake 189 and TOX3069-66-2-1-6 lowland rice cultivars grown in an iron-toxic soil, Korhogo, Côte d'Ivoire.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	CK4	Bouake 189	TOX3069-66-2-1-6
No fertilizer	4.3 (3)	3.4 (5)	2.9 (7)
N	4.4 (3)	4.1 (5)	3.3 (7)
N + P	5.3 (2)	4.3 (4)	4.2 (5)
N + K	4.8 (2)	4.4 (4)	3.8 (5)
N + Zn	4.8 (2)	4.6 (4)	4.6 (5)
N + P + Zn	5.0 (2)	4.4 (4)	4.2 (4)
N + K + Zn	5.2 (2)	4.6 (3)	4.6 (4)
N + P + K	5.4 (2)	4.5 (3)	4.5 (3)
N + P + K + ZN	5.7 (2)	4.7 (3)	4.7 (3)
LSD (0.05)	1.01	1.02	1.15

^aIron toxicity scores are given in parentheses. Results are av of 4 years (1995-98).

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Relationship between applied potassium and iron toxicity in rice

S.K. Sahu, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry and B. Sandha, Department of Plant Breeding and Genetics, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology (OUAT), Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa; G. Dev, Potash and Phosphate Institute, Canada-India Programme, Gurgaon, Haryana, India

Highly weathered soils that are acidic, low in bases, deficient in P and K, and rich in sesquioxides occur on 11.7 million ha in India (Prasad and Biswas 2000) and 0.75 million ha in Orissa (Sahu 1993). Rice grown in low- to medium-elevation lands with this type of soil and adjacent to leached uplands often suffers from Fe toxicity associated with interflow of water from the uplands. The mechanism by which interflow exacerbates the toxicity is uncertain, but it appears to involve dilution of plant nutrients and upsetting of the plant's ability to exclude toxic Fe, rather than the inflow of large amounts of dissolved Fe (van Breemen and Moormann 1978). Related to this, the application of liberal doses of K has been found to reduce Fe toxicity in rice and increase yields.

To investigate the relationship between K application and Fe toxicity under these conditions and interactions with climate and

genotypes, field experiments were conducted for three wet seasons (WS, 1991-93) and two dry seasons (DS, 1993-94) on an iron-toxic soil at the Central Research Station of OUAT in Bhubaneswar. The soil is an Aeric Haplaquept derived from highly weathered material, with pH 4.9, CEC 4.4 cmol_c kg⁻¹, 0.36% organic C, 10 ppm Olsen's P, 51 ppm NH₄OAc K, and 398 ppm DTPA-extractable Fe. Treatments included five K levels (0, 33, 66, 99, and 132 kg K ha⁻¹) and four rice varieties—Mahsuri in the WS and Parijat in the DS (tolerant of Fe toxicity) and Jaya in the WS and Pathara in the DS (susceptible to Fe toxicity).

The experimental design was a split plot with rice varieties in the main plot and K levels in the subplots, replicated three times. All treatments received 80 kg N and 18 kg P ha⁻¹ as urea and single superphosphate, respectively. Nitrogen was applied in three splits (25% at transplanting,

50% at mid-tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation). All the P and 50% of the K were applied at transplanting with the rest of the K at 25 d after transplanting (DAT). The K used was muriate of potash.

Symptoms of Fe toxicity appeared in the control and lowest K plots at 25 and 30 DAT in susceptible varieties in the WS and DS, respectively. Symptoms were reddish brown spots on the tips of lower leaves with bronzing, later spreading over the entire leaf. The intensity of bronzing decreased with K application. Bronzing symptoms were scored at 40 DAT according to the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* (IRRI 1980). Data (Table 1) showed that, among the four rice varieties tested, Jaya and Pathara were more susceptible to Fe toxicity than Mahsuri and Parijat. Toxicity scores were higher during the WS than during the DS and in the year with higher rain-

fall and more rainy days. Presumably, this was due to the greater upwelling of water during the wetter season. The toxicity score decreased with K addition.

Grain and straw yields (Table 2) under different treatments varied in different years with differences in climate and intensity of Fe toxicity. Both grain and straw yields increased with the addition of K in all varieties.

The effect of K on yield was greatest in the years that produced the greatest Fe toxicity. The application of 132 kg K ha⁻¹ increased average grain yield by 136% in Jaya, 71% in Pathara, 59% in Mahsuri, and 42% in Parijat. The response to K application was greater in WS varieties than in DS varieties. The effect of K application on straw yields was similar to that on grain yields.

References

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Table 1. Effect of K application on Fe toxicity of susceptible and tolerant rice varieties during wet and dry seasons (1 = least severe, 9 = most severe).

K level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Wet season						Dry season			
	Jaya			Mahsuri			Pathara		Parijat	
	1991	1992	1993	1991	1992	1993	1992–93	1993–94	1992–93	1993–94
0	7	9	9	2	3	3	7	7	3	3
33	7	7	7	1	3	3	5	7	3	3
66	5	5	5	1	2	2	5	5	2	3
99	5	5	5	1	1	1	3	3	1	2
132	3	3	3	1	1	1	3	2	1	1

Table 2. Effect of K application on yield of susceptible and tolerant varieties grown in Fe-toxic lateritic soil, Orissa, India, 1991–93 wet seasons and 1993–94 dry seasons.

K level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Wet season								Dry season					
	Jaya				Mahsuri				Pathara			Parijat		
	1991	1992	1993	Mean	1991	1992	1993	Mean	1992–93	1993–94	Mean	1992–93	1993–94	Mean
<i>Grain yield (t ha⁻¹)</i>														
0	1.3	1.1	0.7	1.3	2.1	1.8	1.6	1.8	2.1	1.7	1.9	2.7	2.4	2.4
33	1.5	1.2	1.3	1.4	2.6	2.1	1.8	2.2	2.3	2.1	2.2	3.1	2.9	3.0
66	2.1	1.7	2.1	1.9	2.2	2.2	2.4	2.3	3.0	2.5	2.7	3.2	3.2	3.2
99	2.2	2.0	2.4	2.2	2.8	2.4	2.7	2.6	3.0	2.9	3.0	3.4	3.3	3.4
132	2.6	2.2	2.5	2.4	3.2	2.6	2.8	2.9	3.2	3.3	3.2	3.7	3.6	3.6
Mean	1.9	1.6	1.8	–	2.6	2.2	2.3	–	2.7	2.5	–	3.2	3.1	–
<i>CD (0.05)^a</i>														
K	0.38	0.13	0.25						0.30	0.18				
V	0.49	0.16	0.15						0.13	0.10				
K × V	ns	ns	0.15						ns	ns				
<i>Straw yield (t ha⁻¹)</i>														
0	1.6	1.3	0.8	1.2	3.0	2.2	1.7	2.5	2.3	1.9	2.1	3.0	2.3	2.7
33	2.0	1.6	1.4	1.7	3.6	2.8	1.9	2.8	2.7	2.3	2.5	3.4	3.0	3.2
66	2.6	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.9	3.5	2.7	3.3	3.2	2.9	3.1	3.6	3.3	3.4
99	3.3	2.8	2.5	2.9	4.2	3.6	2.8	3.6	3.4	3.3	3.4	3.7	3.6	3.6
132	3.5	3.1	2.9	3.2	4.5	3.7	3.0	3.7	3.7	3.6	3.7	3.9	3.9	3.9
Mean	2.6	2.2	1.9		3.8	3.3	2.3		3.1	2.8		3.5	3.2	
<i>CD (0.05)^a</i>														
K	0.52	0.33	0.30						0.24	0.26				
V	0.29	0.30	0.07						0.11	0.18				
K × V	0.29	ns	0.07						ns	ns				

^aCD values refer to a season with two varieties, five treatments, and three replications in a split-plot design.